

ACTIVITY 2.2.2.3: COMMUNITY-LEVEL RISK REDUCTION INTERVENTIONS AT BAT GUANO HARVEST SITES IN KAMPOT AND BATTAMBANG PROVINCES

Participatory Assessment Report *A Report from STOP Spillover Cambodia*

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Cover photo: Female guano harvester group prioritizing seasonal health issues in Battambang province.
Photo Credit: STOP Spillover Cambodia

Strategies to Prevent (STOP) Spillover

Activity 2.2.2.3: Community-level risk reduction interventions at bat guano harvest sites in Kampot and Battambang provinces

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

BBG	Battambang
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
FBG	Female Bat Guano Harvesters
FBGBBG	Female Bat Guano Harvesters in Battambang
FBGKPT	Female Bat Guano Harvesters in Kampot
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
KAP	Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices
KPT	Kampot
MBG	Male Bat Guano Harvesters
MBGBBG	Male Bat Guano Harvesters in Battambang
MBGKPT	Male Bat Guano Harvesters in Kampot
OH-DReaM	One Health Design, Research and Mentoring
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
STOP Spillover	Strategies to Prevent Spillover
TTBGKPT	Traders-cum-Transporter of Bat Guano in Kampot
WG	Working Group

STOP Spillover

Strategies to Prevent Spillover (or STOP Spillover) enhances global understanding of the complex causes of the spread of a selected group of zoonotic viruses from animals to humans. The project builds government and stakeholder capacity in priority Asian and African countries to identify, assess, and monitor risks associated with these viruses and develop and introduce proven and novel risk reduction measures. “Spillover” refers to an event in which an emerging zoonotic virus is transferred from a non-human animal host species (livestock or wildlife) to another, or to humans.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Strategies to Prevent Spillover (STOP Spillover) Cambodia Country Team carried out a preliminary participatory investigation to explore the livelihoods and practices of bat guano harvesters in Kampot and Battambang, Cambodia. The field assessment emphasized community engagement and collaborative intervention design. Eighty-four stakeholders including 53 bat guano harvesters from diverse backgrounds participated in community dialogues, representing different ages, genders, and roles involved in the bat guano harvesting process. All groups acknowledged some inherent risk in bat guano harvesting; however, awareness of zoonotic diseases varied, and women generally demonstrated more awareness of these risks. Inconsistent hygiene practices and a lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) pose significant challenges.

All groups reported respiratory issues, skin irritations, and broader health problems; specific problems varied by group and season. For example, chronic cough was a major problem for some, while skin problems were more prevalent during specific seasons. Both communities discussed ways to identify key interventions to mitigate these health problems, such as the use of fabric masks, fabric gloves, proper handwashing, and regular clothes washing. However, the groups identified cost, availability, practicality, and comfort as barriers to successful implementation.

The bat guano harvesters highlighted health problems due to inadequate hygiene, exposure to dust and irritants in the caves, and limited access to PPE. While these communities demonstrated a proactive approach in identifying, proposing, and prioritizing solutions, overcoming resource and accessibility barriers remains crucial. The co-design process resulted in several potential interventions, including the suboptimal use of PPE and improved hygiene practices tailored to each group's needs. Promoting proper hand hygiene through readily available handwashing stations and training on proper techniques was recommended. Encouraging PPE use involves selecting appropriate options for specific work environments, ensuring affordability and accessibility, and promoting proper maintenance and use.

STOP Spillover Cambodia attempted to achieve active community engagement in and ensure sustainability of its interventions through collaborative design, fostering community ownership, and utilizing local knowledge. Addressing cost and availability barriers requires partnerships with relevant stakeholders, exploring local sourcing of materials, and finding creative solutions. Finally, promoting practicality and comfort through user-centered design and ongoing feedback loops from the communities is essential to ensure interventions are comfortable, practical for daily use, and sustainably adopted.

By implementing these collaborative interventions, addressing knowledge gaps, and prioritizing hygiene, PPE use, and overcoming accessibility barriers, we can effectively reduce zoonotic

spillover risks and support the well-being of bat guano harvester communities in Cambodia. This comprehensive approach, built on collaboration and community empowerment, holds the potential for a healthier and more sustainable future for all involved.

I.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Southeast Asia, including Cambodia, harbors diverse bat populations known to carry zoonotic coronaviruses, posing a potential threat for human spillover (Tang et al. 2006; Latinne et al. 2020). One key interface driving this risk is bat guano harvesting in caves, a widespread practice in Cambodia fueled by the high value of guano as fertilizer for crops like durian and black pepper. While it does produce a valuable product, this activity also exposes harvesters to direct contact with bat droppings and urine, creating opportunities for viral transmission through multiple pathways (Tang et al. 2006). Additionally, indirect exposure occurs for individuals visiting caves for religious, cultural, or other purposes (Tang et al. 2006). Further amplifying risk, bat hunting and consumption are widespread and involve intimate contact with potentially infected animals (Phauk et al. 2013).

Building on previous successful interventions with bat guano farmers and their neighbors in the Kampong Cham province, STOP Spillover Cambodia is launching a new initiative in Kampot (KPT) and Battambang (BBG) provinces that began with site selection activities in late 2023. Based on the report of the site selection activities, this new initiative will engage individuals involved in bat guano harvesting activities in caves, including harvesters, sack sealers, carriers, and traders-cum-transporters, to collaboratively design and implement interventions that effectively mitigate zoonotic spillover risks from these livelihoods in the bat-human-bat interface created by the caves.

This report presents findings from two community dialogues conducted as part of a participatory assessment process. Community dialogues are a participatory, interactive communication process aimed at reaching a common understanding and workable solutions to address any perceived challenges or to solve community problems. The community dialogues engaged a diverse, broad base of participants including community members and leaders, representatives from provincial departments of environment, health, and agriculture, guano harvesters, transporters, and traders, to gain a deeper understanding of existing the bat-human interface, perceived risks, current practices, and potential risk reduction interventions. By incorporating these diverse voices, the STOP Spillover team strives to develop context-specific, sustainable joint solutions that address potential spillover risks in target communities.

Figure 1. Selected provinces for the study Kampot (bottom) and Battambang (top)

1.2 Objectives

The objectives of the participatory assessment were to:

1. Engage bat guano collection communities in KPT and BBG provinces to assess their knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to zoonotic disease risk.
2. Jointly identify possible risk reduction practices with the greatest potential to reduce zoonotic spillover risk and identify any barriers to adopting those safety practices.
3. Foster collaboration among stakeholders to develop and co-create effective, localized solutions for reducing risk at the bat-human high-risk interface.
4. Lay the groundwork to promote the expansion of successful risk reduction interventions through community-driven adaptation and implementation in new cave-associated bat guano harvest sites.

2.0 METHODS

2.1 Programs and Facilitators

The community participatory assessment program included a comprehensive series of activities, including facilitator training sessions and community dialogues conducted in KPT and BBG. Training sessions were tailored for both national and subnational government officials who were appointed as One-Health Design for Research and Mentoring (OH-DReaM) Working Group (WG) members and assisted the country team as facilitators (Table I).

Facilitators' Guideline Training: Twenty-five officials from the two locations were trained as co-facilitators, with 11 from KPT and 14 from BBG. This training focused on orienting government officials about community level discussions in advance of the dialogues. This prepared them to co-facilitate community dialogues with the STOP Spillover country team.

Table I. Summary of programs and facilitators

Location	Facilitator Training	
	OH-DReaM WG member	# of person(s)
Kampot (KPT)	Department of Communicable Diseases Control (Cambodia)	1
	General Department of Animal Health and Production	1
	Provincial Department of Environment	1
	Provincial Department of Agricultures, Forestry and Fisheries	1
	Provincial Department of Health	1
	Office of Health Operating District	1
	Health center	1
	Commune Committee for Women and Children	1
	District Vet	1
	Village Chief	1
	Community leader	1
Subtotal	11	

Battambang (BBG)	Department of Communicable Diseases Control (Cambodia)	1
	General Department of Animal Health and Production	1
	Provincial Department of Environment	1
	Provincial Department of Agricultures, Forestry and Fisheries	1
	Provincial Department of Health	1
	Office of Health Operating District	1
	Health center	3
	Commune Committee for Women and Children	1
	District Vet	1
	Village Chief	2
	Community leader	1
Subtotal	14	
Total	25	

2.2 Data Collection, Recording, and Presentations

2.2.1 PROCESSES AND INFORMANTS

This study employed focus group discussions (FGDs)—a participatory approach—to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (including biosafety and biosecurity practices, bat guano handling) of individuals involved in the bat guano industry. This collaborative approach actively engaged participants throughout the research process. The aims were to establish a baseline and identify acceptable and sustainable interventions promoting zoonotic disease prevention and control within their communities. The main participants in the process comprised 59

stakeholders, including bat guano harvesters (45), seamstresses (5), bat guano carriers (3), and traders-cum-transporters (6) as presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Focus group participants in community dialogues

Group	No. of Female Participants	No. of Male Participants	Total Participants	Comment
Female Bat Guano Harvesters in Kampot (FBGKPT)	12	0	12	All female bat guano harvesters in KPT
Male Bat Guano Harvesters in Kampot (MBGKPT)	0	16	16	All male bat guano harvesters in KPT
Traders-cum-Transporter of Bat Guano in Kampot (TTBGKPT)	3	3	6	Half of bat guano traders/transporters in KPT
Female Bat Guano Harvesters in Battambang (FBGBBG)	13	0	13	All female bat guano harvesters in BBG
Male Bat Guano Harvesters in Battambang (MBGBBG)	0	12	12	All male bat guano harvesters in BBG
Total	28	31	59	

2.2.2 Data Collection

During the FGD, the Country Team and OH-DReaM WG members – the team – used two data collection tools: (i) KAP questionnaire and (ii) consultative dialogue baseline information collection tool.

2.2.2.1 KAP QUESTIONNAIRE

The KAP questionnaire (Annex 4) consists of three sections, which assessed participants' KAP regarding zoonotic diseases:

- **Section 1 (seven questions):** Knowledge and perception of zoonotic diseases and related factors.
- **Section 2 (five questions):** Attitudes towards bat-associated diseases.

- **Section 3 (nine questions):** Self-reported risk management practices and good practices within the communities.

Responses of the participants to each question of relevant sections were noted. The participants then voted for each of the responses by raising their hands. The team recorded, counted, and converted their votes to percentages for analysis.

2.2.2.2 CONSULTATIVE DIALOGUE BASELINE INFORMATION COLLECTION TOOL

The consultative dialogue baseline information collection tool (Annex I) covered five aspects: (i) risk identification, (ii) cause and effect analysis, (iii) solution identification, (iv) intervention identification and (v) intervention co-design. The team employed three methods to facilitate open discussions and gather information on these five aspects.

- **Plenary session:** All participants came together to discuss and reach consensus on specific topics.
- **Open discussion:** The team gave each group time for group reflection and discussion about the topics generated in the plenary session.
- **Scoring:** The team gave each group 100 candies for them to vote for answers/problems they agreed upon/listed. For example, they can assign one candy or 100 candies to an answer/a problem; and then the proportional allocation was calculated as a percentage for each answer/problem.

In both KAP and baseline data collection processes, qualitative statements from the FGDs were also collected and reported in this participatory assessment report.

2.3 Consultation and Co-design Process

This assessment used a co-design process, which actively involved community members in identifying and addressing their own health concerns. Through a series of participatory activities, community members collaborated in recognizing challenges, analyzing their impact, and co-designing interventions to mitigate them. This approach fosters a sense of ownership and ensures that interventions respond to the specific needs and context of the community.

This process sought to foster community participation and prioritize participants' views on their health issues. This was achieved through various activities that encourage active engagement from community members. This collaborative approach ensured that the assessment captured the collective voices and insights of the community, leading to a more comprehensive and relevant understanding of their health concerns. The steps are below:

- **Risk Identification:** Community members in different break-out groups participated in a simple listing exercise to identify and list various health issues prevalent in the community. This exercise provided an opportunity for community members to voice their concerns and contribute to the identification of key health risks. Using the proportional piling method, a tool from participatory epidemiology, each group distributed 100 candies among the listed health risks, ranking and prioritizing the top five risks based on the distribution of candies. Additionally, a seasonal calendar for each health risk by month was created using the proportional piling method to identify the seasonal occurrence of each risk, providing valuable insights into the temporal patterns of health risks within the community.
- **Causes and Effects Analysis:** A problem tree analysis was utilized to analyze each health issue together with its root causes and the impacts as felt by the participants. This visual representation provided a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between the identified risks, their causes, and their effects on the community. By engaging in this analysis, each group of community members gained insights into the underlying factors contributing to the identified health issues and their potential impacts on the community's well-being.
- **Solution Identification:** Community members engaged in open discussions and a plenary session to identify potential solutions to address identified health issues. This participatory approach enabled community members to share their knowledge, experiences, and perspectives, contributing to the identification of contextually relevant and feasible solutions. The open dialogue fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange, ensuring that the solutions were informed by community insights and priorities.
- **Intervention Identification:** The community engaged in a simple listing exercise to identify interventions that could be implemented to address identified health issues. This process provided an opportunity for community members to contribute their ideas and suggestions for potential interventions. Additionally, participants used the proportional piling method to prioritize and select the most effective interventions by distributing 100 candies proportionally among listed interventions. This approach enabled the community to collectively prioritize and select interventions based on their perceived effectiveness and relevance.
- **Intervention Co-Design** Community members participated in open discussions and a plenary session to co-design selected interventions, ensuring that interventions were tailored to community needs and preferences. This collaborative approach empowered community members to actively contribute to the design and development of interventions, fostering a sense of ownership and ensuring that interventions were appropriate and responsive to each community's unique context.

The participatory co-design process empowered the community to actively engage in the assessment and decision-making process, ensuring that the resulting interventions were informed by community insights and priorities. Microsoft Office Excel was used for data storage, processing, and initial analysis.

It should be noted that all data presented in this report is not taken from a random sample of bat guano harvesters, but from non-randomly selected focus group discussion participants. Data cannot, therefore, be extrapolated to a wider audience.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Characteristics of Target Groups who Participated in FGDs

Five groups (Table 2) participated in community dialogues. Members of participants in the five groups comprised 47 percent women. These groups were: (i) the female bat guano harvesters in Kampot (FBGKPT), (ii) the male bat guano harvesters in Kampot (MBGKPT), (iii) the traders-cum-transporters in Kampot (TTBGKPT – half men, half women), the female bat guano harvesters in Battambang (FBGBBG), and all male bat guano harvesters (MBGBBG). All participants were between 18 and 70 years old (Figure 1).

The majority of community dialogue participants were in the 31–50 year age range. There were fewer young people involved in community dialogues in BBG than KPT, and more elderly women participated in community dialogues as representatives of bat guano harvesters in KPT than BBG. Representatives of traders-cum-transporters aged between 31 and 60 years old.

Figure 2. Age distribution of participants in community dialogues, by gender, geography, and type

Table 3 illustrates the percentage of participants in various roles, including harvesters, carriers, movers, transporters, sealers, and traders/transporters. The table also illustrates the distribution of responsibilities across different groups, shedding light on the diverse roles undertaken by participants.

Table 3. Roles of men and women in different bat guano harvesting processes

Group Type	Bat Guano Harvesters (# of persons)	Bat Guano Carriers (# of persons)	Seamstresses (# of persons)	Trader-cum-Transporter (# of persons)
FBGKPT	12	0	0	0
MBGKPT	13	3	0	0
TTBGKPT	0	0	0	6 (3 females)
FBGBBG	10	0	3	0
MBGBBG	10	0	2	0

The data suggests a potential specialization based on gender within the KPT group. Females exclusively engage in harvesting, while males participate in both harvesting and carrying. In contrast, the BBG group shows no gender-based specialization, with both sexes involved in multiple roles. The KPT group seems to emphasize harvesting and trading/transporting, with minimal involvement in mover or seller roles. Conversely, the BBG group exhibits a more diverse distribution of roles, with participation in harvesting, transporting, and selling, but not trader-transporter functions.

This glimpse into the division of labor highlights the influence of both gender and location in the bat guano industry. KPT leans towards specialization, while BBG thrives on collaboration. Understanding these dynamics empowers stakeholders to craft targeted interventions, address specific needs, and promote sustainable practices that consider the unique makeup of these communities.

Participants in each target group had a range of educational backgrounds, ranging from no education, or primary education only, to university-level education. Figure 2 illustrates the educational diversity among the participants in the community dialogue, providing insight into the distribution of educational experience across different groups.

Our analysis reveals several interesting patterns regarding educational attainment in bat guano harvesting communities. Both KPT and BBG groups show higher rates of “no education” among men compared to women. This suggests potential inequities in access to education or differing societal priorities based on gender. Primary education dominates across the board, highlighting limited accessibility or pursuit of higher education within these communities by bat guano harvesters. The exception is male harvesters in the KPT group, where primary education is

second to high school education. This suggests a nuanced difference in the educational landscape in KPT compared to BBG. The BBG group exhibits greater diversity in educational attainment, with male bat guano harvesters having primary, secondary, and even high school education. This hints at potentially different dynamics within this group compared to the KPT group.

The BBG Group: Belonging to the Phnom Romsay Sak Forestry Protected Community (Annex 9a), this group benefits from a more structured system. The community committee manages guano collection areas for members, sets fair prices, schedules sales, and guards the cave. Additionally, they control and distribute collective benefits equitably among members, ensuring a sense of shared responsibility and financial security.

The KPT Group: In contrast, the KPT group, under the Phnom Kuhear Loung Forestry Protected Community (Annex 9b), operates with a less structured system. While the community committee still manages guano collection areas, sets fair prices, schedules sales, and guards the cave, individual harvesters are responsible for managing their own benefits or losses. This difference suggests a potential lack of shared financial support within the KPT group.

3.2 Knowledge, Attitudes and Current Risk Management Practices Among FGD Participants

3.2.1 Target Group Knowledge of Zoonotic Diseases

This section explores the knowledge and awareness of zoonotic diseases among individuals involved in bat guano harvesting and trading (Table 4). The information is based on responses from participants in community dialogues, and while potentially indicative of broader attitudes and practices within these groups, it is important to note that these participants cannot be considered a statistically representative sample of the entire bat guano harvesting population.

However, by analyzing KAP of these participants, we gained valuable insights into potential risks associated with bat guano harvesting and identified areas where education and intervention are crucial. To ensure participants' understanding of zoonotic diseases before assessing their KAP, a brief educational session employing demonstrations was conducted (details in Annex 8). Additionally, the assessment employed a collective method for the KAP assessment. Participants responded to questions by raising their hands (a quick and convenient way to gauge group opinion) if the answer was positive, allowing for a collective understanding of the community's KAP concerning their health.

Table 4. Questions related to knowledge and perception of zoonotic diseases

Questions	Simplified questions used to ask the communities
Q5. Have you known or heard about zoonotic diseases?	Do you know what zoonotic diseases are? (Or, simpler yet:) Have you heard of diseases that can jump from animals to people? How many of you all know/hear, raise your hands.
Q5.1. Are you aware that animals are capable of transmitting diseases to humans?	How many of you all have heard animals can sometimes make people sick? Raise your hands.
Q5.2. Are you aware that living and working close to the bats can increase risk of contracting certain diseases?	We know some diseases can spread from animals to humans. (Raise your hand if you think being around bats a lot could increase the chances of getting sick.)
Q5.3. Do you know how the diseases are transferred from the bats to humans?	Some diseases can spread from animals to humans. Can you (raise your hand) share your thoughts on how these diseases might be transmitted from bats to humans?
Q5.4. Could list/name any disease that can be transferred from animals to humans?	We know some diseases like Rabies can spread from animals to humans. Have you heard of any other diseases that can be transmitted from animals to people, similar to Rabies? (Raise your hand if you have heard of any.)
Q5.5. Do you know any signs or symptoms that bats show when they are sick?	We've discussed bats and potential health risks. (Raise your hand if you know any signs that might indicate a bat is sick.)
Q5.6. Could list or name any of the signs and symptoms of bat-related diseases?	Some common signs of illness in humans include fever, coughing, and fatigue. (Raise your hand if you can think of any similar signs or symptoms that someone might experience if they were sick from contact with bats.)

Table 5 summarizes the knowledge and awareness of zoonotic diseases and related factors within each group.

Table 5. Knowledge and awareness of zoonotic diseases and related factors within each group

Variables		Knowledge related to zoonoses (percent of community dialogue participants)				
		FBGKPT	MBGKPT	TTBGKPT	FBGBBG	MBGBBG
Knowledge of zoonoses (%)		57	29	100	100	58
Awareness of disease transmission from animals to human (%)		57	21	100	100	92
Awareness of contracting diseases if lived and worked with bats (%)		0	100	17	38	83
Perception of bat-to-human risks (%)		0	0	100	0	8
Knowledge of specific zoonotic diseases (%)	COVID-19	0	0	50	38	25
	Nipah Virus (NiV)	0	0	16.7	0	16.7
	Ebola	0	0	0	0	0
	Avian Influenza	35.7	79	16.7	15.4	8.3
	Rabies	57.1	21	16.7	15.4	8.3
	Histoplasmosis	7.1	0	0	0	0
Knowledge of signs/symptoms of sick bats (%)		0	50	0	15.4	50
Knowledge of signs/ symptoms of bat-related diseases (%)		0	71	0	15.4	33

In assessing these responses, it is important to remember that coronaviruses have never been clearly shown to be directly transmitted to humans from bats. Severe acute respiratory syndrome, or SARS, and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, or MERS, are transmitted to humans via bridging hosts (civets and camels respectively). Similar process has been suggested also for SARS-CoV2, also known as the 2019 coronavirus or COVID-19, though the pathway of

zoonotic transmission for this virus is not known. As the risk of direct transmission is unknown, we use the term “perception of risk” rather than “awareness of risk.”

Women bat guano harvesters in KPT stand out as being more aware of zoonoses and the possibility of bat-to-human disease transmission, at 57 percent. Their male counterparts (MBGKPT) show lower awareness, with only 29 percent recognizing zoonoses, with 21 percent acknowledging bat-to-human transmission as a potential risk. The transport and trade group in KPT demonstrates very high awareness of both concepts, suggesting they could play an important role in bringing about more comprehensive knowledge in other stakeholder groups by sharing zoonotic disease information more widely with bat guano harvesters.

In BBG, male bat guano harvesters showed a high level of awareness of bat-to-human transmission risks (92 percent) and the inherent risks associated with their work (83 percent). However, their understanding of other potential threats like Ebola (0 percent), Histoplasmosis (0 percent), Avian Influenza (8.3 percent), Rabies (8.3 percent), Nipah virus (16.7 percent) and COVID-19 (25 percent) remains limited, though some of these are indeed unlikely in SE Asian bats. This uneven awareness of specific diseases suggests targeted education efforts could be beneficial.

For knowledge regarding bat health, MBGBBG demonstrate awareness of sick bats and their symptoms (50 percent), which could facilitate monitoring and surveillance of general health status of bat colonies.

3.2.2 Attitudes Towards Risk

Section 2 of the KAP assessment questionnaire focused on understanding the target community's attitudes towards bat-related diseases. The following questions were included in this section (Table 6).

Table 6. Questions related to attitudes towards health problems

Questions	Simplified questions used to ask the communities
<p>Q6. Do you agree or disagree that your attitudes or activities lead to contracting bat diseases?</p>	<p>We've learned about zoonotic diseases and their transmission. Please share your observations or concerns about how people's interactions with bats might be related to health risks. "Agreement with the question was indicated by participants raising their hands and sharing opinions, which were then recorded."</p>
<p>Q6.1. Do you agree or not that eating and drinking with bat-guano contamination increases the risk of getting bat-related zoonotic disease?</p>	<p>We have discussed bats, bat guano, and potential health risks. Can you share your thoughts on how activities like eating or drinking near bat guano might be related to the risk of contracting zoonotic diseases?" Agreement with the question was indicated by participants raising their hands and sharing opinions, which were then recorded."</p>
<p>Q6.2. Do you agree or not that having direct contact with guano, urines and carcasses increases the risk of getting bat related zoonotic disease?</p>	<p>Can you share your thoughts on how activities involving bats, such as handling guano, urine, or carcasses, might be related to the risk of contracting diseases? "Agreement with the question was indicated by participants raising their hands and sharing opinions, which were then recorded."</p>
<p>Q6.3. Do you agree or not working in the cave does not put you at risk of contracting bat related zoonotic disease?</p>	<p>We've discussed bats, their habitats, and potential health risks. Can you share your thoughts on how working in caves, where bats might be present, might be related to the risk of contracting zoonotic diseases? "Agreement with the question was indicated by participants raising their hands and sharing opinions, which were then recorded."</p>
<p>Q6.4. Do you agree or not bat droppings/manure contain any infectious disease agent?</p>	<p>Can you share your thoughts on whether bat droppings (also called guano) might be a potential source of any diseases? "Agreement with the question was indicated by participants raising their hands and sharing opinions, which were then recorded."</p>

The awareness of zoonoses varies across bat guano harvester groups, with notable differences observed between female and male harvesters from different locations. Both FBGKPT and FBGBBG demonstrate a high awareness of zoonoses, with a reported awareness of 100 percent (Table 7). In contrast, their male counterparts show lower but still moderate awareness, with 29 percent and 58 percent of male bat guano harvesters demonstrating awareness of zoonoses

in KPT and BBG respectively. All of the traders and transporters in KPT exhibited some knowledge of zoonotic diseases, possibly due to their roles, or greater access to news and social media.

Table 7. Knowledge of zoonotic diseases and attitudes towards risks

Type of group	Zoonoses knowledge (%)	Attitudes/ activities lead to bat diseases (%)	Eating/ drinking with contamination increases risk (%)	Direct contact with guano/ urine/carcasses increases risk (%)	Working in cave increases risk (%)	Bat droppings contain infectious agents (%)
FBGKPT	57	0	0	0	0	0
MBGKPT	29	64	0	0	0	0
TTBGKPT	100	100	100	0	0	0
FBGBBG	100	100	85	100	54	0
MBGBBG	58	25	85	67	75	83

Despite having lower knowledge of zoonoses (29 percent), MGBKPT were likely to believe their attitudes or activities could lead to bat-related diseases (64 percent). Neither female bat guano harvesters nor male bat guano harvesters in KPT perceived a direct link between their work and disease risk. Risk perception was higher in both male and female bat guano harvesting groups in BBG.

The understanding of transmission routes also varies among the groups, with some groups (TTBGKPT and male and female bat guano harvesters in BBG) acknowledging increased risk associated with eating/drinking contaminated materials. However, some discrepancies exist. For instance, the FBGBBG expressed uncertainty (54 percent) about risks working in the cave itself, despite acknowledging the risk from direct contact with contaminated materials. A greater percentage of MBGBBG believed that working in the cave posed a risk (75 percent).

In general, male and female bat guano harvesters in KPT perceive less risk than those in BBG from their work. However, TTBGKPT do perceive risks from bat guano harvesting, but not from coming into contact with guano, urine, or carcasses.

3.2.3 Current Risk Management Practices

During community dialogues the team assessed the self-reported risk management practices of different bat guano harvesting groups. This section primarily used questions to explore good practices and activities adopted by these communities. The following details the specific questions used in this section (Table 8).

Table 8. Questions related to current risk management practices

Questions	Simplified questions used to ask the communities
Q7. Do you currently follow any specific practices to minimize health risks when working with bats or bat guano?	We've discussed bats and potential health risks. Can you share any practices you use to minimize health risks when working with bats or bat guano?" raise your hands.
Q7.1. Are you usually eating snacks and drinking during bat-guano collection?	Can you raise your hands if you eat and drink while harvesting guano?
Q7.2. Do you wash your hands before eating and drinking when you are inside and outside the caves?	Could you tell me if there are specific hygiene protocols in place for handling bat guano, such as washing hands before eating and drinking, both inside and outside the caves? Please raise your hands.
Q7.3. Do you wash your hands after attending to any of the caves/harvesting bat guano?	Please raise your hands if you wash your hands after leaving the caves or handling with guano.
Q7.4. Do you think washing hands is important after handling the bat guano?	Is handwashing crucial for minimizing health risks after handling bat guano? Please raise your hands if you think it is crucial.
Q7.5. Do you always apply soap when washing hands?	Is soap always used when washing hands? Please raise your hands if you use soap when washing your hands.
Q7.6. Do you use any protective clothing before attending to the caves?	Could you tell us the type of personal protective clothing used when entering the caves? Please raise your hands.
Q7.7. Do you usually change clothes after leaving the caves?	Please raise your hands if you remove your dirty cloth after leaving the cave.
Q7.8. Do you use a face mask when attending any of the caves?	Please raise your hands if you wear a face mask when entering the cave.

While some groups demonstrated promising approaches, the data reveals gaps and inconsistencies, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. The following summarizes our findings, which are further illustrated in Table 9:

Knowledge of Zoonoses: Data revealed that women bat guano harvesters in KPT and BBG demonstrated high awareness of zoonoses, exceeding 50 percent, suggesting potential for understanding the risks associated with bat-borne diseases. In contrast, MBGKPT exhibited lower awareness (29 percent) compared to their female counterparts, indicating a knowledge gap that could be addressed through education programs. TBBGKPT shows complete knowledge of zoonoses, possibly due to their role requiring broader understanding of associated risks.

Risk Management: 100 percent of TTBGKPT and 42 percent of MBGBBG regularly used at least one of the specified risk management practices. Conversely, FBGKPT and MBGKPT had considerably lower awareness at 14 percent and 36 percent, respectively, highlighting potential areas for improvement in their understanding of risk assessment and mitigation strategies. Notably, none of the women bat guano harvesters in BBG reported any existing risk management practices, suggesting a need for intervention and education in this group. Full details of the questionnaire section on risk management are found in Annex 4 (Q7.1-7.8).

Hygiene Practices: Eating and drinking within the cave during guano collection is not uncommon among various groups, it's important to understand the associated health risks. Due to the long working hours and difficulty navigating in and out of the caves, taking breaks to eat and drink outside can be time-consuming and challenging. No bat guano harvesters in KPT and BBG, regardless of gender, reported washing their hands before eating or drinking, with the exception of TTBGKPT, where 100 percent of workers claimed to practice hand hygiene before meals. Such practices can contaminate their food and drinking water and pose health risks.

Handwashing outside the caves and after harvest is inconsistent among FBGKPT, MBGKPT, and TTBGKPT. Unlike the KPT groups, FBGBBG and MBGBBG practice handwashing outside of the caves. Only MBGBBG reported using soap when handwashing. This suggests the need for promoting hand hygiene routines and improving the use of soap.

Table 9. Percentage of responses to current risk management practices

Variables (Type of group)	Percentage of responses				
	FBGKPT	MBGKPT	TTBGKPT	FBGBBG	MBGBBG
Knowledge of Zoonoses	57	29	100	100	58
Risk Management Practices	14	36	100	0	42
Eating/Drinking During Collection	100	100	100	100	33
Handwashing Before Eating/Drinking (Cave)	0	0	100	0	0
Handwashing Before Eating/Drinking (Outside Cave)	0	0	100	100	100
Handwashing After Harvest	100	100	100	92	100
Soap Used for Handwashing	0	7	0	0	100
Protective Clothing	0	0	0	8	67
Change Clothes After Leaving Cave	0	0	100	100	100
Face Mask Use	0	0	100	8	42

Protective Clothing: None of the groups use specialized personal protective equipment (PPE). However, MBGBBG (67 percent) and FBGBBG (8 percent) reported using two layers of clothes to protect themselves from bat waste and insect bites. This suggests gaps in inappropriate personal protection, especially regarding potential airborne contaminants.

Changing Clothes After Leaving Cave: TTBGKPT, FBGBBG, and MBGBBG reported changing their clothes after leaving the cave, demonstrating a potentially impactful risk reduction practice. In contrast, FBGKPT and MBGKPT did not change their clothes after leaving the cave. They return home in their work clothes, which are usually dirty.

3.3 Risk Analysis

3.3.1 Health Problem Identification

The term "health risk" refers to a potential threat that could cause harm to individuals' well-being. According to the Environmental Protection Agency, health risks are defined as "the chance of harmful effects to human health or to ecological systems resulting from exposure to an environmental stressor." Therefore, a human health risk is characterized as "the likelihood that a given exposure or series of exposures may have damaged or will damage the health of individuals" (EPA 2016).

3.3.1.1 WEEKLY ACTIVITY PROFILES BY GENDER

An analysis of the weekly activities of male and female bat guano harvesters in the two provinces reveals a deeply ingrained division of labor based on gender (as described in Table 10). While both men and women contribute to the family income, their roles and daily experiences differ significantly.

In KPT, every morning, both men and women embark on their shared morning ritual: preparing essentials for the day, especially food. Snacks are packed, lunches made, and plans to venture into the cave to harvest bat guano are made. This shared responsibility emphasizes a collaborative spirit, where gender takes a backseat to essential community tasks. However, as the afternoon sun sets, a stark contrast emerges. Women's work includes a whirlwind of domestic activity: tending to children, tackling housework, haggling at the market, and preparing evening meals. Their days are woven with the threads of care and responsibility, leaving little room for personal leisure.

Meanwhile, men embark on a different path. Their afternoons are occupied with social interactions, spending time catching up with friends and enjoying leisure activities. This stark difference suggests a potential "leisure gap" between genders, where the burden of domestic tasks falls heavily on women, while men have more freedom for personal pursuits.

"Sunup, everyone is at it - packing food, getting ready for the caves. Down there, it is men and women side-by-side, a team effort. But when the sun dips low, that is where things change. Our world turns into a whirlwind - kids, chores, markets, meals. Feels like there's no time to breathe, let alone relax. Meanwhile, the men are catching up with friends, enjoying their free time. It is not fair, is it? This gap between us, where the weight of everything falls on our shoulders. We all work hard, but the time to rest. That seems to be a privilege some folks have, and others don't." - A FBGKPT

Table 10. Gender-based activities in bat guano harvesting communities

Time of Day	Harvesting schedule			
	Once every 6 weeks		Every day	
	BBG		KPT	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
Morning	Bat guano harvesting	Prepare snacks, pack lunch, chores, bat guano harvesting	Bat guano harvesting	Chores, prepare snacks, pack lunch, bat guano harvesting
Afternoon	Agriculture, socializing	Childcare, housework, market visit, meal prep	Social interaction	Childcare, housework, market visit, meal prep
Evening	Bat guano harvesting	Bat guano harvesting	Rest	Rest
Seasonal Closure	August and September	August and September	None (Daily harvest)	None (Daily harvest)

In BBG, women shoulder the burden of domestic work throughout the week, juggling childcare, housework, market visits, and meal preparation. Even their mornings are split, balancing preparations for bat guano work with household chores. On the other hand, men primarily focus on bat guano harvesting in the mornings, followed by agricultural work, and socializing in the afternoons. Notably, women and men engage in additional bat guano harvesting at night.

For the BBG community, a common practice in guano harvesting is seasonal closure of the caves. Every year the bat guano harvest is closed during August and September when local people are busy with their farming, and heavy rains make access to the cave dangerous. Unfortunately, this closure does not align with the breeding season of the bats (October to December), a time when virus shedding has been reported to be highest. In addition to seasonal closure, the bat guano harvest only occurs at night. The combination of these two practices means that bat guano harvesters in BBG have less contact with bats. In the case of seasonal closure, they have less contact with bats through the year while in the case of night harvest they also have less contact because bats are nocturnal mammals and are not in the cave at this time. This also reduces the potential level of bat disturbance.

However, these practices are not followed in KPT where bat guano harvesters harvest guano every day, year-round, and they harvest during the daytime. Seasonal closures would not be possible under the current system, because harvesters depend on bat guano harvesting for their

daily income. They also cannot harvest at night because their cave is far away from their villages and visibility and access to the cave are very bad.

" Here in Kampot, it's harvested every day, rain or shine. We cannot afford to wait for the rains to stop or the bats to breed, our families depend on this guano." - A MBGKPT.

3.3.1.2 HEALTH CONCERNS OF BAT GUANO HARVESTERS: A CLOSER LOOK

This section delves into the self-reported health issues faced by bat guano harvester groups, shedding light on their concerns and potential contributing factors (Table II).

Respiratory symptoms: A common thread across all groups is the high prevalence of respiratory symptoms, with chronic cough, breathing difficulties, and influenza-like illness consistently reported. This suggests potential exposure to dust, airborne contaminants, or even respiratory infections. Further investigation is needed to pinpoint the exact causes and explore preventive measures.

Table II. Reported health issues faced by the target group

Group Name	Reported health problems
FBGKPT	Nerve disorder, fever, dizzy, headache, stomachache, eye soreness, waist soreness, flu, persistent cough, back pain, breathing difficulty
MBGKPT	Nose soreness, dengue, ear soreness, fever, headache, eye soreness, malaria, flu, typhoid, skin rash (itching)
TTBGKPT	Perception of increased risk of various zoonotic diseases, flu, COVID-19, chronic cough, dengue, rabies, breathing difficulties
FBGBBG	Skin problems (itching), sore eyes, flu, sore throat, cough, difficulty breathing, fatigue, stomachache, dengue fever, arthritis, blood depression, diarrhea, dizziness, bloody diarrhea, stomach pain
MBGBBG	Sore throat, red eyes, headache, skin problems, vomit, fever, suffocation, muscle aches, nasal congestion, cough, sneeze, swollen feet and hands, other symptoms/illnesses

Skin Irritation: Both male and female harvesters, particularly those in BBG frequently reported skin rashes and itching of their hands. This indicates the need for improved hygiene, PPE use and protective measures, as direct contact with guano and other irritants is a possible culprit.

Eye Strain: Several groups mention eye soreness and redness, which could be attributed to exposure to dust and other irritants. Ensuring proper use of eye protection and minimizing exposure to dust may reduce the incidence of this problem.

Beyond the obvious: While respiratory, skin, and eye issues dominate the conversation, other concerns like fever, dengue and muscle aches are also mentioned. Additionally, the female harvester group in KPT raised concerns about fatigue, stomach problems, and high blood pressure. These broader health concerns warrant further investigation to understand their root causes and implement appropriate interventions.

"The cough will not leave me, and my eyes sting all day. Sometimes, it is hard to even breathe. This work takes a toll, more than just on our lungs." –A FBGKPT.

"Flu is bad, but the dust gets to your eyes too. Sometimes I worry about the rashes, and even getting sick like others with malaria. This job comes with risks." –A MBGKPT.

"The itching drives me crazy, and my throat feels raw. But it is the tiredness that worries me most. I wonder if all this guano is making me sick inside." –A MBGBBG.

3.3.1.3. HEALTH RISK RANKING AND PRIORITIZATION

After communities listed all of their health concerns, the STOP Spillover team listed reported symptoms and asked participants to rank them. By analyzing the top five reported symptoms and their corresponding percentages for each group, we explored prevalent health concerns and priorities within these two communities (Table 12). This data provides a foundation for understanding the specific health issues faced by each group and underscores the importance of tailored interventions and targeted health initiatives.

Table 12. Ranking of major health issues across groups

Group Name	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5
FBGKPT	Flu (33%)	Persistent cough (27%)	Eyes soreness (17%)	Headache (14%)	Breathing difficulty (9%)
MBGKPT	Flu (60%)	Eyes soreness (20%)	Breathing difficulty (10%)	Skin rash (itching) (6%)	Malaria (4%)
TTBGKPT	Chronic cough (30%)	Breathing difficulty (26%)	Flu (22%)	COVID-19 (12%)	Various zoonotic diseases (10%)
FBGBBG	Flu (28%)	Skin Rash (itching) (26%)	Sore throat (21%)	Persistent coughing (15%)	Eyes soreness (10%)

Group Name	Rank 1	Rank 2	Rank 3	Rank 4	Rank 5
MBGBBG	Skin rash (itching problem) (64%)	Eyes soreness (Red eyes) (15%)	Breathing difficulty (8%)	Flu (7%)	Fever (6%)

FBGKPT: While flu and persistent cough top their list, priority diseases extended beyond these two issues. They also frequently experience eye soreness, headaches, and difficulty breathing.

MBGKPT: While flu was their primary concern, eye soreness and respiratory issues like difficulty breathing are also prioritized. This group additionally reported skin rashes, possibly linked to their work, and malaria, which may reflect specific regional health risks.

TTBGKPT: Chronic cough and breathing difficulty dominated their concerns, likely due to dust exposure during transportation. Interestingly, they also expressed fear of contracting various zoonotic diseases, highlighting their awareness of potential risks associated with their trade.

FBGBBG: Flu and skin problems were their main battles, followed by sore throat and persistent cough. However, their concerns extended to fatigue, stomach issues, and dizziness, requiring additional investigation. This potentially broader impact on their overall health warrants further exploration.

MBGBBG: Skin problems dominated this group, followed by eye issues and breathing difficulties. Notably, they mentioned muscle aches, fever, and even swollen limbs, suggesting potential musculoskeletal and circulatory concerns beyond the typical respiratory and skin complaints.

3.3.1.4 DISEASE SEASONAL CALENDARS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

The listed health issues were ranked, and then each target group focused their efforts on tackling the top five most frequent seasonal concerns (listed in Table 13). Participants allocated more resources to the most common issues they faced, based on the season. For a full list of diseases by season, refer to Annex 5.

"These caves are not exactly health spas. My lungs always feel like sandpaper during the dry season, dusty cough keeping me awake. Then the rains come, and it is the skin that flares up. Guess there is no perfect time to be down there, but hey, we do what we must do." - A MBGBBG.

"The health issues. We all know them, the coughs, the rashes, the chills that come with the damp. But fear of what might happen pales in comparison to the fear of what will happen if we do not go down there. This bat guano, it is our lifeline, and even if it comes at a cost, it is a cost we are willing to pay." - A FBGKPT.

Table 13. Seasonal calendar of health problems

Seasonality		Dry Season				Rainy Season						Dry Season	
		Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Health Issues													
1	Skin rash												
2	Flu (sneezing, runny nose, fever, headache)												
3	Eyes soreness (red eyes)												
4	Breath difficulty												
5	Persistent cough												

Key Findings:

- **Respiratory Issues:**

- Flu-like illness: Primarily occurs during the dry season across most groups, aligning with typical flu seasonality. However, the FBGKPT experiences a secondary peak in colder months (November - February).
- Persistent cough: Primarily affects harvesters during the dry season for the FBGKPT and TTBGKPT.
- Difficulty breathing: Shows varying patterns. The FBGKPT and TTBGKPT experience peaks during the dry season, potentially linked to dust and colder temperatures. However, the MBGBBG reports year-round difficulties.

- **Other Concerns:**

- Skin rash: Primarily occurs during the rainy season for most groups, possibly due to increased moisture, irritants, or fungal growth. The MBGKPT exhibits the highest prevalence (90 percent).
- Eye soreness: Shows diverse patterns. The FBGKPT and MBGBBG experience peaks during the rainy season, while the MBGKPT and TTBGKPT see them in the dry season, suggesting both seasonal and cave environment factors might be involved.
- Headaches: Primarily reported during the rainy season by the FBGKPT, potentially linked to environmental factors or stress.
- Malaria: Shows an expected peak during the rainy season (mosquito breeding) for the MBGKPT.
- Zoonotic diseases: The TTBGKPT reports a potential peak towards the end of the dry season, warranting further investigation into specific diseases and contributing factors.

3.3.2. Identified Health Issues: Cause and Effect Analysis

Table 14 below presents the diverse health issues encountered by individuals involved in the bat guano harvesting industry.

Table 14. A comparative analysis of health issues faced by target groups

Health issues	Participant-identified root causes	Impacts experienced
Sore Eyes	Deficient hygiene practices (inadequate handwashing, touching eyes with contaminated hands), environmental pollutants (dust, sweat, insect incursion)	Diminished economic opportunity, financial burden due to medical care, potential transmission within community, job displacement, unproductive time (FBGBBG)
Flu	Inadequate sanitation measures (not utilizing masks, neglecting hand hygiene), airborne contaminants (dust, noxious odors), thermal stressors (extreme cold/heat), deleterious personal habits (smoking, alcohol consumption) (MBGBBG)	Financial hardship, increased healthcare costs, potential community spread, compromised child health (FBGKPT), diminished revenue, deterioration of well-being, unproductive time (MBGKPT and MBGBBG)
Skin Rash (Itching)	Arthropod bites, insufficient hygiene practices (inadequate handwashing, improper attire), interaction with guano/urine, elevated temperatures	Reduced income, financial strain due to medical care, unproductive time, job loss (MBGKPT) - diminished economic output, compromised health (MBGBBG)
Persistent Cough	Dust-laden environment, noxious odors, thermal stress	Pulmonary impairment, sleep disturbances, physical debilitation, diminished economic opportunity (FBGKPT)
Difficulty Breathing	Airborne contaminants (dust, odors), confined spaces, extended work periods	Shortness of breath, dizziness, exhaustion, death (MBGKPT) - suffocation, physical weakness, lost work time (MBGBBG)
Chronic Cough (TTBGKPT)	Dust-laden air, contaminated objects touching mouth/nose, airborne particles in vicinity of guano handling, influenza, dusty roads	Sleep disruption, financial burden due to medical care, potential transmission within community, diminished income
Malaria (MBGKPT)	Mosquito bites during nighttime work	Compromised health, reduced work capacity, financial strain due to medical care
COVID-19 (TTBGKPT)	Inadequate physical distancing, insufficient hygiene practices (inadequate handwashing), lack of facial coverings	Community transmission, quarantine measures, lost income, social stigmatization

Health issues	Participant-identified root causes	Impacts experienced
Zoonotic Diseases (TTBGKPT)	Interaction with infected animals (touching, consumption), deficient hygiene practices, disruptive interactions with wildlife.	Mortality, loss of economic opportunity, legal repercussions

Across all groups, inadequate hygiene and biosafety practices like lack of handwashing, gloves, and masks emerge as a central theme, facilitating the spread of influenza-like illnesses and ocular irritation from dust and contact with guano and urine. Thermal stressors in the form of extreme cold or heat further exacerbate respiratory problems like persistent cough and respiratory distress associated with working in confined spaces. These risks translate into diminished economic opportunities due to lost work time and increased healthcare costs, perpetuating a cycle of hardship.

Group-Specific Concerns:

- FBGKPT and FBGBBG:
 - Skin inflammation from insect bites and poor hygiene, impacting their well-being and productivity.
 - Experience headaches potentially linked to hot and stuffy cave environments, requiring further investigation.
- MBGKPT and MBGBBG:
 - Skin inflammation and the threat of malaria from night-time mosquito bites, jeopardizing their health and income.
 - Suffer from nose soreness and difficulty breathing, possibly linked to extended work hours in enclosed cave environments.
- TTBGKPT:
 - While they may not directly interact with guano in caves, exposure to dust during transportation and handling can still lead to respiratory problems like coughing and breathing difficulty.
 - They face risks associated with long working hours and strenuous physical activity, potentially leading to musculoskeletal problems.

- Interaction with individuals from various backgrounds poses a risk of transmitting and contracting infectious diseases, including COVID-19, highlighting the importance of hygiene and social distancing practices.

Photo 1. Result written on problem-tree for cause analysis in BBG

3.3.3 Solution Identification

Across all groups, respiratory problems like flu, cough, and sore throat pose a significant threat to the health of bat guano harvesters and traders-cum-transporters (Table 15). Implementing simple yet effective measures such as wearing masks, maintaining hand hygiene, and avoiding smoking and alcohol consumption proves crucial in mitigating these risks. Additionally, avoiding contact with infected bats further safeguards against potential zoonotic disease transmission.

"You say working in the caves is tough. Yes, it is, but the real challenge is remembering everything you need to do to stay healthy.If I can think of ways to keep myself safe, I think dust masks for the coughs, long sleeves for the rashes, mosquito repellent for the bites... and do not forget to wash everything, down to the last shoes! It's like being a doctor, a fashion designer, and a janitor all rolled into one. But at least we are prepared for anything that comes our way, right?" - A FBGBBG with a sense of humor.

"They say this guano is like gold, but let me tell you, it does not come without its price. Every time I head down into that cave, it is a battle – dust in my lungs, sweat stinging my eyes, and the constant worry of catching something nasty. But then I remember my family, the bills piling up, and I know I got to push through. It is not easy, but sometimes you have to risk a little health for a whole lot of hope." - A MBGKPT struggling to make ends meet.

Table 15. Health issues and solutions identified by communities during dialogues

Group	Health issues	Key solutions identified by participants
All Groups	Flu, Cough, Sore Throat	Mask, hand hygiene, avoid smoke/alcohol and avoid infected bats
All Groups	Eye Sore	Glasses, gloves, eye drops
All Groups	Skin Rash	Wash hands/body/clothes, protective clothing, insect repellent
FBG/MBG (KPT, BBG)	Breath Difficulty	Work in well-ventilated areas, mask/Krama (traditional scarf)
MBGKPT	Malaria	Mosquito protection (clothing, repellent)
TTBGKPT	COVID-19	Mask, social distancing, hand hygiene
TTBGKPT	Zoonotic Diseases	Avoid contact with sick animals, good hygiene
FBGKPT	Headache	Stay hydrated, manage heat stress, take breaks in fresh air

Protecting Eyes:

Eye health is seen as important, regardless of group. Community members emphasized the importance of wearing glasses/goggles and gloves while handling guano, along with utilizing eye drops when necessary.

Preventing Skin Rashes:

Skin rashes are another prevalent concern. Solutions identified by communities included: consistent washing of hands, body, and clothes, coupled with the use of protective clothing and insect repellent.

Group-Specific Concerns and Solutions:

While some health issues are universal, certain groups face specific challenges:

- **FBG/MBG (KPT & BBG):** Individuals in these groups often experience breathing difficulties due to working in confined spaces and dust exposure. Working in well-ventilated areas and using masks or kramas was suggested.
- **MBGKPT:** Malaria poses a specific threat to this group due to nighttime work. Mosquito protection measures like protective clothing and repellent are essential. (Note: While

malaria was raised as an issue primarily by men, it is presumably a risk equally to women when they are exposed to the same conditions).

- TTBGKPT: This group mentioned increased risks of COVID-19 and zoonotic diseases due to interactions with various individuals. Masks, social distancing, and meticulous hand hygiene were mentioned as their primary lines of defense.
- FBGKPT: This group mentioned frequent headaches, potentially linked to working in hot and stuffy environments. Staying well hydrated, managing heat stress, and taking breaks in fresh air might offer relief.

3.4 Interventions and Co-Design

3.4.1 Intervention Identification and Selection

Both the KPT and BBG groups actively identified and addressed health and safety concerns within their communities during plenary sessions. The KPT group, consisting of FBG, MBG and TTBG, identified nine potential practices for reducing health risks (Table 16). These practices include two key interventions: (i) use of PPE and (ii) improved hygiene practices. PPE use included suggestions of wearing fabric masks, fabric gloves, fabric hats and dedicated work clothing. Hygiene practices mentioned include handwashing with soap, provision of readily available handwashing stations, and daily washing of designated work clothes. Through a prioritization process, the group identified six key practices from the two categories, reflecting a comprehensive approach to health and safety.

Table 16. List of interventions identified, prioritized and co-designed for implementation in KPT

Intervention Activities		Intervention 1: Suboptimal Use of PPE					Intervention 2: Hygiene Practices			
1	Identified									
		Fabric Mask	Fabric Gloves	Safety boots	Fabric Hat	Plastic Face Shield	Raincoat	Hand Washing	Hand Washing Station	Daily Wash of Designated cloth
2	Prioritized									

Note:

- (check mark) indicates the intervention was prioritized by the group.
- (cross mark) indicates the intervention was not prioritized by the group.

"I want all people in this community to be safe while working in the caves, men and women alike. That is why we came together and listed down some important things, like wearing masks and gloves, washing our hands properly, and keeping our clothes clean. It is a team effort, and we are all looking out for each other." - A KPT Provincial Department of Environment Official.

"Cave dust is not exactly friendly, but neither are we. We all, men and women, put our heads together to figure out how to stay safe down there. Masks, gloves, clean clothes, hand washing - it might seem simple, but it keeps us going. This is not a one-person job; we are going to look out for each other in these caves." - A FBGKPT.

"Cave dust? It is a nightmare, no doubt. Makes you cough and wheeze something fierce. But we got to keep going, right? ...But as known, those masks and gloves they say we are going to wear? They are not cheap, and some folks just cannot afford them. We have to look out for each other, that is for sure, but it is not easy when the tools to stay healthy cost an arm and a leg. This is not right; you know what I mean?" - A BBG Bat Guano Harvester

Similarly, the BBG group, including both female and male members, displayed a proactive stance during their session. They identified seven risk reduction practices aimed at mitigating health risks within their community (Table 17). Participants prioritized five practices from the identified interventions, focusing on wearing fabric masks and gloves, wearing hats, thorough handwashing with soap, and wearing dedicated work clothing, washed daily after each use.

These interventions reflect a thoughtful and proactive approach to addressing health and safety concerns within the BBG group. Overall, the identification and prioritization of these interventions by both the KPT and BBG groups underscore a commitment to promoting a safe and healthy environment for their members. These efforts demonstrate a collaborative approach to addressing potential health and safety risks, reflecting a commitment to the well-being of their communities.

Table 17. List of interventions identified, selected and co-designed for implementation in BBG

Intervention		Intervention 1: Suboptimal Use of PPE				Intervention 2: Hygiene Practices		
Activity								
1	<i>Identified</i>							
		Fabric Mask	Fabric Gloves	Fabric Hat	Raincoat	Hand Washing	Hand washing Station	Daily Wash of Designated Cloth
2	<i>Prioritized</i>							

Note:

- (check mark) indicates the intervention was prioritized by the group.
- (cross mark) indicates the intervention was not prioritized by the group.

3.4.2 Intervention Co-Design and Commitments

Both the KPT and BBG groups prioritized health and safety measures after extensive discussions and co-design. Amongst all target groups, their rates of commitment for implementing the selected practices are highlighted in Table 18. For a full record of their responses, refer to Annex 6.

The KPT group identified four key practices for immediate implementation:

1. **Wearing fabric gloves:** Protects hands from direct contact with contaminated guano, reducing skin irritation and disease transmission.
2. **Wearing fabric hats:** Minimizes dust exposure and helps prevent inhalation of harmful particles.
3. **Consistent handwashing with soap:** Ensures proper hand hygiene, preventing the spread of bacteria and viruses encountered during guano harvesting.
4. **Daily washing of designated clothing:** Regular laundering minimizes the risk of harboring harmful contaminants on clothes worn during harvesting activities.

Similarly, the BBG group committed to five key practices for immediate action:

1. **Wearing fabric masks:** Protects individuals from dust, airborne pathogens, and other respiratory hazards.
2. **Wearing fabric gloves:** Protects hands from direct contact with contaminated guano, reducing skin irritation and disease transmission.
3. **Wearing fabric hats:** Minimizes dust exposure and helps prevent inhalation of harmful particles.
4. **Consistent handwashing with soap:** Ensures proper hand hygiene, preventing the spread of bacteria and viruses encountered during guano harvesting.
5. **Daily Washing of Designated Clothing:** Regular laundering minimizes the risk of harboring harmful contaminants on clothes worn during harvesting activities.

Table 18. Analysis of commitment rates for selected good practices of the two interventions

Risk Reduction Practices	Commitment, percentage of members in each group	Notes
Fabric Gloves	36% (MBGKPT) 100% (TTBGKPT) 58% (MBGBBG) 77% (FBGBBG)	High awareness of hand protection importance.
Fabric Masks	62% (FBGBBG) 50% (MBGBBG) 100% (TTBGKPT) 0% (FBGKPT) – possible reasons: cost, comfort, use of alternative face coverings (krama scarves).	Significant variation
Boots	None	Issue with cost, availability, or practicality in cave environment
Fabric Hats	43% (FBGKPT) - 100% (TTBGKPT) 100% (FBGBBG and MBGBBG)	Understanding the importance of head protection from dust
Glasses/goggles	None	Gap in eye protection
Raincoats	None	Potential cost or practicality concerns
Handwashing with Soap	100% (TTBGKPT) 50% (FBGKPT) 71%. (MBGKPT)	Inaccessibility to handwashing facilities and lack of hygiene practices
Handwashing Stations	None	Issue with cost and availability
Daily Washing of Designated Clothes	71% (MBGKPT) - 100% (TTBGKPT)	High awareness of maintaining proper hygiene by cleaning harvest clothes

3.4.3 Challenges Implementing Selected Interventions

Following discussions about potential interventions for bat guano harvesting safety, both the KPT and BBG groups faced challenges implementing some of the proposed solutions. These challenges primarily revolved around cost, availability, comfort, and practicality in the context of their working environments.

"We got to be smart about how we protect ourselves. Masks might be good, but down in those hot, cramped caves, they make it hard to breathe. That's why we use our Krama scarves - they're cheap, readily available, and do the trick most of the time." - A MBGKPT.

"Boots sound good, but let's be honest, they're expensive and hard to come by around here. We got to work with what we have, and sometimes, that means getting our shoes a little dirty. It's all about finding a balance between safety and what's practical for us." - A FBGKPT.

Cost and Availability:

- **Face Masks:** The KPT group expressed a preference for readily available and reusable Krama scarves as an alternative to purchasing additional face masks, mitigating unnecessary expenses.
- **Boots:** The high cost and potential difficulty in obtaining boots, especially in resource-limited communities, posed a significant barrier to their widespread adoption.
- **Raincoats:** The perceived unnecessary expense of wearing an extra layer, particularly in hot climates, led to lower prioritization of raincoats.
- **Face Shields:** Compared to readily available Krama scarves, face shields might be costlier or less accessible, hindering their adoption by some individuals.

Practicality and Comfort:

- **Face Masks:** Working in confined spaces with limited air circulation, the KPT group found face masks uncomfortable and potentially hindering their breathing, especially during physically demanding tasks.
- **Boots:** Depending on the specific terrain and working conditions, boots could be cumbersome and restrict movement, impacting work efficiency.
- **Raincoats:** The added layer of a raincoat in hot weather could lead to discomfort and potentially hinder physical performance.
- **Face Shields:** Some individuals might find face shields bulky and restrictive, impacting their daily activities and potentially leading to lower acceptance.

3.5 Discussion

By employing community dialogues in KPT and BBG provinces, the STOP Spillover team was able to shed light on the intricate relationship between bat guano harvesting and zoonotic disease risk in Cambodia. These findings highlight the diverse experiences and perspectives of stakeholders involved, paving the way for collaborative interventions. The community dialogues played an important role in building trust and shared understanding between participants and project staff regarding the risks, the challenges and the potential barriers to successful risk reduction.

KAP:

The variation in awareness of zoonoses across different groups (e.g., female harvesters demonstrating higher awareness) underscores the need for targeted education programs (Baker et al. 2015; Ninsiima et al. 2024) tailored to specific knowledge gaps and demographics. While focusing initial efforts on groups with higher awareness (e.g., female harvesters) can be efficient, neglecting other groups could perpetuate existing inequalities and leave them vulnerable (Williams et al. 2023). The acknowledged importance of handwashing, although inconsistently practiced, signifies the need for hygiene promotion campaigns (Morales-

Betancourt et al. 2015; Furey et al. 2018) that address barriers (e.g., lack of water, soap) and emphasize critical moments for handwashing (e.g., before and after handling guano). The absence of PPE use necessitates interventions that go beyond awareness. Exploring cost-effective, culturally appropriate PPE options (Williams et al. 2023) and promoting consistent use alongside proper hygiene practices are crucial. Collaborations with local producers/vendors and involvement of communities in designing comfortable, practical solutions can improve adoption rates (Ninsiima et al. 2024).

Health Problems and Seasonality:

The prevalence of respiratory problems, skin irritation, and other health problems associated with harvesting activities necessitates comprehensive health assessments to better understand the scope and impact of these risks (Morales-Betancourt et al. 2015). Identifying the seasonal variation in health problems such as flu-like illness and skin problems informs targeted interventions aligned with specific periods of heightened risk (Furey et al. 2018).

Community-Led Interventions:

Both communities identified proven risk reduction interventions like masks, gloves, and handwashing (Ninsiima et al. 2024), demonstrating their willingness to participate in risk reduction strategies. Addressing barriers like cost, availability, and comfort is critical for successful implementation. Collaborating with local vendors, exploring cost sharing (Furey et al. 2018), and involving communities in designing comfortable, practical solutions are vital steps.

4.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 *Conclusions*

This participatory assessment conducted using collaborative dialogues with bat guano harvesting communities in Kampot (KPT) and Battambang (BBG), Cambodia, offers a compelling look into the day-to-day lives, practices, and perspectives of guano harvesters and traders. It goes beyond demographics to paint a multifaceted picture encompassing their knowledge, attitudes, and the alarming health risks they face.

These findings reveal a concerning reality: communities are grappling with significant health problems likely in part due to their work in bat caves. This environment creates exposure to dust, irritants, and potentially infectious pathogens, compounded by inadequate hygiene and biosafety practices and a lack of personal protective equipment (PPE). Respiratory problems, skin irritations, and broader health concerns were reported across all demographic groups, highlighting the pervasive nature of these risks. Interestingly, while the concept of zoonoses remained unfamiliar to some, female harvesters demonstrated a deeper understanding of the potential for animal-to-human disease transmission. Despite varying levels of awareness, one crucial aspect remained constant - everyone acknowledged the inherent risks associated with their work, and many participants attributed much of their ill-health to the work.

However, amidst these challenges, a glimmer of hope emerges. The study found that both communities were proactive in identifying interventions they believed could improve their situation. This included widespread use of fabric masks (only female bat guano harvesters FBG and male bat guano harvesters MBG in BBG and traders-cum-transporter of bat guano in KPT (TTBGKPT) and fabric gloves, consistent handwashing practices, and proper clothes washing after work. This awareness, desire for solutions, and expressed willingness to try new safety practices, pave the way for collaborative efforts.

These findings serve as a call to action. While highlighting the health risks, the study also underscores these communities' understanding and eagerness for change. This opens doors for collaboration between healthcare professionals, farmers, traders, community leaders, and relevant authorities to implement interventions proposed by the harvesters themselves. By providing education, ensuring access to PPE, and promoting consistent hygiene practices, local actors can empower these communities to safeguard their health while sustaining their livelihoods.

This collaborative approach, guided by both scientific expertise and the lived experiences of the harvesters, holds the potential to create a future where these communities thrive, free from the preventable health risks they currently face. It's a future where their valuable contribution to the agricultural sector is recognized and accompanied by the tools and knowledge they need to work safely and securely.

4.2 Recommendations

Drawing upon the insights gleaned from this study as well as the previous work of Strategies to Prevent Spillover (STOP Spillover) with guano farmers in Kampong Cham, the STOP spillover team proposes a comprehensive action plan to address the health issues faced by bat guano harvesters in the two target provinces, while empowering them to continue their livelihoods safely. These recommendations prioritize targeted interventions, community engagement, and overcoming barriers to achieve sustainable improvements.

Hygiene and Personal Protection:

- **Handwashing and Hygiene:**
 - Wherever possible, install cost-effective handwashing stations with soap and water near cave entrances.
 - Educate communities on proper handwashing techniques before and after work, and before eating/drinking.
 - Encourage carrying small bars of soap or hand sanitizer for situations without handwashing stations.
 - Wash designated work clothes each day after harvesting or handling bat guano.
- **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):**
 - Fabric Gloves: Promote fabric gloves (e.g., cotton) to protect hands from contact with guano and reduce skin irritation.
 - Fabric Hats: Promote fabric hats or scarves to cover heads and minimize dust exposure.
 - Fabric Masks: Depending on comfort and practicality, consider options like reusable cloth masks or disposable masks specifically designed for dust protection. Even woven cloth face coverings can provide ~50 percent protection from the coarser particles that are most common in animal manure dust (Lee et al. 2021, Sweeten et al. 1998). Prioritize masks in high-risk situations or for individuals with concerns.

- **Education and Awareness:**

Zoonosis and Disease Prevention: Develop educational programs in local languages that address:

- The risks of zoonotic diseases from bats and how to minimize contact.
- The importance of hygiene practices in preventing the spread of germs.
- Safe handling procedures for guano and other materials.
- Recognizing signs and symptoms of potential illnesses and seeking medical attention if needed.
- Seasonal Health Risks: Educate communities about the health risks specific to different seasons and recommend appropriate preventative measures (e.g., wearing warmer clothes in colder months).

- **Community Engagement and Sustainability:**

- Work with community leaders and organizations: Partner with trusted individuals and groups to ensure interventions are culturally sensitive and effectively reach those in need.
- Involve communities in decision-making: Encourage participation in designing and implementing interventions to foster ownership and sustainability.
- Explore locally available resources: Identify affordable and accessible materials for PPE and hygiene practices.
- Monitor and evaluate interventions: Regularly assess the effectiveness of implemented measures and adapt them as needed.

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ANNEX I: COMMUNITY DIALOGUE AND FACILITATOR'S GUIDELINES

STOP Spillover Cambodia

Activity 2.2.2.3: Community-level Risk Reduction Interventions in Kampot and Battambang provinces

Community Dialogue Guideline

Behavior Risk Reduction and Social Behavior Change

Instructions and materials

- a) This instrument briefly describes what to do in and how to do the community dialogue for A.2.2.2.3.
- b) Facilitators work in a team of two (lead and assistant facilitators) and should focus the process on **bat-human interface risks**. *Hints for facilitators: (i) risks along bat-guano activity chain: collection, packaging, storing, transporting, and using (of bat guano); (ii) risks regarding locations: at bat caves, in communities, and in households; and (iii) risks regarding livestock and pets: straying, roaming and scavenging livestock (cattle, buffaloes, goats, ducks, chickens, pigs, etc.), and uncaged pets (dogs, cats, etc.).* Themes to be kept in mind and reflected in all discussions include belief, knowledge, attitudes, behaviors, and practices; gender; and social and household structure and power.
- c) Build trust and intimacy with the participants.
- d) The lead facilitator facilitates the group discussions and prepare all inputs from the participants on the given flipcharts. The inputs provided by the participants should be prepared as pictures, in drawings, and in writings legible to and understandable by the participants. The prepared inputs **MUST** be nice and neat. The assistant facilitator **MUST** take notes from the discussions and transcribe all inputs from the flipcharts to the given journals/notebooks. The flipcharts **CAN** be left with the communities afterward.
- e) Lead question terms that can be used by the facilitators are what, which, why, where, how, when, who/whom. Never hint any answers. Always have follow-up questions for specificity.
- f) Make sure that no authorities influence the discussions, and no particular participants dominate the discussions.
- g) Materials needed include flipcharts, markers, pens, pencils, buttons, journals/notebooks, scotch tapes, etc.

Process and steps

Process and steps to follow in and to implement the community dialogue (CD) are presented hereunder.

Step I: Mobilization of community

- Send formal letter/s to provincial and local authorities to request for permission, coordination, and participation for/in organizing community dialogues. The letter/s **MUST** clearly state objectives, purposes, and processes; specify date/s, time/s and location/s; and identify target participants of the CD.
- Confirm their approval and participation.
- Organize the community dialogue/s (in the field).

Step 2: Community dialogue

Step and what	Who, lead question, and how
<p>Step 2-1: Introductory / start-up session (plenary)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome and give orientation/a brief project introduction. - State the purposes of the CD. - Provide a brief and simple overview of zoonotic diseases (STOP Spillover TL or PHD/PDAFF). - Breakout group discussions (bat-guano and non-bat-guano households' representatives). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assign one person as a facilitator. - Assign one person to deliver the welcoming message and a brief orientation about STOP Spillover and purposes of the CD. - Assure participants of their rights and consents. - Explain the purposes of group discussions and processes (facilitator).
<p>Step 2-2: Problem identification session (breakout groups)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify and list all identified problems. - Rank all identified problems. - Select five highest ranked problems (to be addressed). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assign a team of two facilitators; one facilitates the discussions and prepares inputs onto the flipcharts while another takes notes. - Lead question: What are the major health risks related to working with caved bat guano (incl., collecting, storing, transporting, selling)? - Give each group 100 buttons, and other materials (incl. markets, flip charts, etc.) - Encourage all participants to identify and list down all relevant problems. - Encourage all participants to prioritize the identified/listed problems using the 100 buttons, and to agree on the final priorities. - Select five top ranked problems, at most, from the above priorities. - Encourage the participants to map locations of the selected top five problems and identify their respective seasonality.
<p>Step 2-3: Problem analysis (breakout groups)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify effects/impacts of the selected problems. - Identify their respective/individual root causes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The same facilitator team from Step 2-2 continues facilitating the group discussions. - Lead question: Why are these health risks present? What are the impacts? - Use problem tree and cause-effect analysis method.
<p>Step 2-4: Solutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify specific solutions to address the root causes of the problems. - Identify appropriate and applicable measures that can help mitigate the severity of the problems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The same facilitator team from Step 2-2 continues facilitating the group discussions. - Encourage the participants to identify and list all possible interventions (solutions or measures and means) to address or mitigate the root causes of the problems.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encourage the participants to choose the interventions that they can practice or implement effectively, efficiently, and sustainably with efficacy using the 100 buttons and assure their agreement on the final choices.
<p><u>Step 2-5: Intervention planning session (plenary)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each group presents their chosen interventions to the community group (in plenary session mode). - Collect all interventions from all groups and build a reconcile list of interventions and present them back. - Schedule the implementation of the interventions and identify interventions implementing actors. - Discuss sources of resources for implementation (own/implementing actors' and/or external/outside [i.e., local agencies, projects]). - Discuss and schedule monitoring and/or evaluation (timing, responsible persons/agencies/authorities, sources of resources). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assign one person as a facilitator. - Assign one or more people to take notes. - Assign one person to prepare inputs onto the flipcharts so that every participant can view.
<p><u>Step 2-6: Commitment/decision session (plenary)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seek commitment of concerned participants (especially, primary bat-guano actors) to implement the identified interventions. - Seek commitment of potential non-bat-guano actors (esp. OH-DReaM WG members, if any, local authorities, etc.) to monitor the implementation, study challenges, collect lessons learned, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assign one person as a facilitator. - Assign one or more people to take notes. - Assign one person to prepare inputs onto the flipcharts so that every participant can view. - Refer to matrices (in Excel file) listing potential interventions for ideas and data to be recorded by the note takers. - Prepare the list of committed interventions using the matrix in Excel file's sheet labelled "InterventionList" as a reference. - Prepare the list of names of people who are committed to certain interventions using the matrix in Excel file's sheet labelled "CommittedPersons" as a reference. - The Excel file is given.

ANNEX 2: FIELD PROGRAM

Project: STOP Spillover Cambodia
Funding agency: USAID
Activity: A2223: Community-level risk reduction interventions at cave-associated bat guano harvest sites in Kampot and Battambang provinces
Sub-activity: Participatory Assessment
Province: Kampot
Duration: JANUARY 02-06, 2024
Contacts: Chhan Ratana (FWA - TECHNICAL SPECIALIST): 069-331-443
 Teng Theara (WLETC): 089-244-503
 Sok Dou (RACTC): 017-592-084

TENTATIVE FIELD PROGRAM

Time	Date (m/d/y)	Activity	Purpose	CT's participating member	Responsible person
Arrangements					
	12/18/2023 - 12/29/2023	- Formal invitation letters for national and subnational stakeholders - Phone calls inviting local authorities (commune, chief) and community leaders - Logistics and accommodation	- to request for permission for fieldwork activities - to get agency's staff to participate in the field activities	Ratana	Ratana
TUESDAY 02 JANUARY 2024					
08:00-11:00	1/2/2024	Travel from Phnom Penh to Kampot province	- to travel from Phnom Penh to Kampot	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
11:00-13:30	1/2/2024	Lunch	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
14:00-15:00	1/2/2024	Check-in Hotel	- to get accommodation	Theara and Ratana	Ratana
15:00-17:00	1/2/2024	Reminders of all volunteer facilitator and going to check/prepare the venue.	- to remind OH-DReaM and community representatives and provincial department officials - to set up the event site for the volunteer facilitator training	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Dou
19:00-21:00	1/2/2024	Dinner	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
WEDNESDAY 03 JANUARY 2024					
06:30-07:30	1/3/2024	Breakfast	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
07:30-08:30	1/3/2024	Travel from Kampot town to Banteay Meas district office	- to travel from town to the event venue	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
08:30-12:00	1/3/2024	Training volunteer facilitators (Refer to attached table of volunteer facilitators)	- explain about Zoonoses, tools, to present and explain community leaders about the agenda, step, process and procedures of community dialogue.	Theara/Ratana	Ratana
12:00-14:00	1/3/2024	Lunch	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
14:00-16:00	1/3/2024	Resume the training session	- to answer questions and solve their concerns before the event, reflection and recommendation - to perform a role play/ rehearsal in facilitating the dialogue (MOCK Community Dialogue)	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Dou
16:00-17:00	1/3/2024	Travel back to Kampot town	- to travel from Banteay Meas District office to Kampot town	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
19:00-21:00	1/3/2024	Dinner	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
THURSDAY 04 JANUARY 2024					
06:00-07:00	1/4/2024	Breakfast	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
07:00-08:00	1/4/2024	Travel from Kampot town to Banteay Meas district office	- to travel from town to the event venue	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
08:00-8:30	1/4/2024	Registration of participants	- to collect participant information and contact	Dou	Dou
08:30-9:00	1/4/2024	Complete a pre-meeting assessment questionnaire (a quick questionnaire provided and answer may go through together as slides shown)	- to gather their perception and prior understanding of risks (initial assessment integrated)	Dou	Dou
09:00-09:30	1/4/2024	Self-introduction	- to get to know each other and warm up the interaction among participants	Theara and Ratana	Theara

09:30-10:00	1/4/2024	Step 2-1: Start-up session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to welcome and give orientation/a brief project introduction and state the purposes of the CD. - to provide a brief and simple overview of zoonotic diseases (STOP Spillover TL or PHD/PDAFF). - to breakout participants into groups 	Theara and Ratana	Theara, PHD's Official
10:00-11:00	1/4/2024	Step 2-2: Problem Identification Session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify and list all identified problems. - to rank all identified problems. - to select five highest ranked problems (to be addressed). 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	TLs and facilitators
11:00-12:00	1/4/2024	Step 2-3: Problem Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to use problem tree and cause-effect analysis method for identifying effects/impacts of the selected problems. - to identify their respective/individual root causes. 	Theara and Ratana	Theara
12:00-13:00	1/4/2024	Lunch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have lunch 	Theara and Ratana	Theara
01:30-02:30	1/4/2024	Step 2-4: Solution Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify specific solutions to address the root causes of the problems. - to identify appropriate and applicable measures that can help mitigate the severity of the problems. 	Dou	Dou
02:30-3:15	1/4/2024	Step 2-5: Intervention Planning Session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to presents their chosen interventions to the community group (in plenary session mode) by each group - to collect all interventions from all groups and build a reconcile list of interventions and present them back. - to schedule the implementation of the interventions and identify interventions implementing actors. 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	TLs and facilitators

03:15-04:30	1/4/2024	Step 2-6: Commitment/decision session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to discuss sources of resources for implementation (own/implementing actors' and/or external/outside [i.e., local agencies, projects]). - to discuss and schedule monitoring and/or evaluation (timing, responsible persons/agencies/authorities, sources of resources). 	Theara and Ratana	Theara
16:30-17:00	1/5/2024	Closing Remarks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to acknowledge and thank you to all participants and stakeholders - to give brief words by participants' interests 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
17:00-18:00	1/5/2024	Travel back to Kampot town	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to travel from Banteay Meas District office to Kampot town 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
19:00-21:00	1/5/2024	Dinner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have meal 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
Friday 05 January 2024					
07:00-09:00	1/5/2024	Breakfast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have meal 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
09:00-12:00	1/5/2024	Travel from Kampot to Phnom Penh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to travel from Kampot province to Phnom Penh 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
END OF THE FIELDTRIP PROGRAMME					

Project: STOP Spillover Cambodia
Funding agency: USAID
Activity: A2223: Community-level risk reduction interventions at cave-associated bat guano harvest sites in Kampot and Battambang provinces
Sub-activity: Participatory Assessment
Province: Battambang
Duration: JANUARY 08-12, 2024
Contacts: Chhan Ratana (FWA - TECHNICAL SPECIALIST): 089-331-443
 Teng Theara (WLETC): 089-244-503
 Sok Dou (RACTC): 017-592-084

TENTATIVE FIELD PROGRAM

Time	Date (m/d/y)	Activity	Purpose	CT's participating member	Responsible person
Arrangements					
	12/18/2023 - 12/29/2023	- Formal invitation letters for national and subnational stakeholders - Phone calls inviting local authorities (commune, chief) and community leaders - Logistics and accommodation	- to request for permission for fieldwork activities - to get agency's staff to participate in the field activities	Ratana	Ratana
MONDDAY 08 JANUARY 2024					
08:00-12:00	1/8/2024	Travel from Phnom Penh to Battambang province	- to travel from Phnom Penh to Battambang	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
12:00-13:30	1/8/2024	Lunch	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
14:00-15:00	1/8/2024	Check-in Hotel	- to get accommodation	Theara and Ratana	Ratana
15:00-17:00	1/8/2024	Reminders of all volunteer facilitator and going to check/prepare the venue.	- to remind OH-DReaM and community representatives and provincial department officials - to set up the event site for the volunteer facilitator training	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Dou
06:30-07:30	1/9/2024	Breakfast	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
07:30-08:30	1/9/2024	Travel from Battambang town to Banan district office	- to travel from town to the event venue	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
08:30-12:00	1/9/2024	Training volunteer facilitators (Refer to attached table of volunteer facilitators)	- explain about Zoonoses, tools, to present and explain community leaders about the agenda, step, process and procedures of community dialogue.	Theara/Ratana	Ratana
12:00-14:00	1/9/2024	Lunch	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
14:00-16:00	1/9/2024	Resume the training session	- to answer questions and solve their concerns before the event, reflection and recommendation - to perform a role play/ rehearsal in facilitating the dialogue (MOCK Community Dialogue)	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Dou
16:00-17:00	1/9/2024	Travel back to Battambang town	- to travel from Banan District office to Battambang town	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
19:00-21:00	1/9/2024	Dinner	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
WEDNESDAY 10 JANUARY 2024					
06:00-07:00	1/10/2024	Breakfast	- to have meal	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
07:00-08:00	1/10/2024	Travel from Battambang town to Banan district office	- to travel from town to the event venue	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
08:00-8:30	1/10/2024	Registration of participants	- to collect participant information and contact	Dou	Dou
08:30-9:00	1/10/2024	Complete a pre-meeting assessment questionnaire (a quick questionnaire provided and answer may go through together as slides shown)	- to gather their perception and prior understanding of risks (initial assessment integrated)	Dou	Dou
09:00-09:30	1/10/2024	Self-introduction	- to get to know each other and warm up the interaction among participants	Theara and Ratana	Theara

09:30-10:00	1/10/2024	Step 2-1: Start-up session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to welcome and give orientation/a brief project introduction and state the purposes of the CD. - to provide a brief and simple overview of zoonotic diseases (STOP Spillover TL or PHD/PDAFF). - to breakout participants into groups 	Theara and Ratana	Theara, PHD's Official
10:00-11:00	1/10/2024	Step 2-2: Problem Identification Session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify and list all identified problems. - to rank all identified problems. - to select five highest ranked problems (to be addressed). 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	TLs and facilitators
11:00-12:00	1/10/2024	Step 2-3: Problem Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to use problem tree and cause-effect analysis method for identifying effects/impacts of the 	Theara and Ratana	Theara
12:00-13:00	1/10/2024	Lunch	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have lunch 	Theara and Ratana	Theara
01:30-02:30	1/10/2024	Step 2-4: Solution Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to identify specific solutions to address the root causes of the problems. - to identify appropriate and applicable measures that can help mitigate the severity of the problems. 	Dou	Dou
02:30-3:15	1/10/2024	Step 2-5: Intervention Planning Session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to presents their chosen interventions to the community group (In plenary session mode) by each group - to collect all interventions from all groups and build a reconcile list of interventions and present them back 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	TLs and facilitators
03:15-04:30	1/10/2024	Step 2-6: Commitment/decision session	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to seek commitment of concerned participants (especially, primary bat-guano actors) to implement the 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
16:30-17:00	1/10/2024	Closing Remarks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to acknowledge and thank you to all participants and stakeholders - to give brief words by participants' interests 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
17:00-18:00	1/10/2024	Travel back to Battambang town	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to travel from Banan District office to Battambang town 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
19:00-21:00	1/10/2024	Dinner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have meal 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Theara
THURSDAY 11 JANUARY 2024					
07:00-09:00	1/11/2024	Breakfast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to have meal 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
09:00-13:00	1/11/2024	Back to Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to travel from Battambang province to Phnom Penh 	Theara, Dou and Ratana	Ratana
END OF THE FIELDTRIP PROGRAMME					

ANNEX 3: LIST OF OH-DREAM WG MEMBERS

Table 19. List of OH-DREAM WG members

Department	Kampot	Battambang
Provincial Department of Environment	Chhim Meng	Soung Piseth
Provincial Department of Health	Touch Sopheary	Sin Sothy
Department of Communicable Disease Control (CDC)	Chieb Sunheng	Chieb Sunheng
District Veterinary Office	Kim SamAnn	Mao Chhoub
General Department of Agriculture	Lim Sophea	Lim Sophea
Provincial Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	Sorng Chea	Uy Vanna
Health Center	In Ratha	Oam Phalline
Provincial Kouprey Living Flora and Fauna Conservation (PKLFPC)	Soung Chern	Lun Bunlern
Village Chief (Chrok Khlai, Bobos)	Chey Puth	Chhao Chhern
Operational District	Chhay Sophea	Khuy Sopheak
Community Forestry and Wildlife Conservation Committee	Lin Chanthorn	Kean Mom
Additional Health Center Representative	-	Thanh Kimkheat
Additional Health Center Representative	-	Phok KoemYi

ANNEX 4: KNOWLEDGES, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICES QUESTIONNAIRE

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ACTIVITY: 2.2.2.3. CAVE-ASSOCIATED RISK REDUCTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS AT THE COMMUNITY LEVELS

Knowledges, Attitudes and Practices (KAPs) Assessment Sheet

Objective: To collect a baseline information of KAPs of zoonoses amongst the participants.

Procedure: This assessment is done early as the beginning of the project and zoonoses briefing. Questions are going one by one amongst the participants under a facilitation by the project team.

Q1. Sex	Male	Female	Mixed			
Q2. Age Group (in years)	Q2.1 18 - 30 y-o	Q2.2 31- 50 y-o	Q2.3 51- 60 y-o	Q2.4 61 - 70 y-o		
Q3. Role Category	Q3.1 Bat Guano Harvester	Q3.2 Bat Guano Carrier	Q3.3 Bat Guano Mover	Q3.4 Bat Guano Transporter	Q3.5 Bat Guano Sealer	Q3.6 Bat Guano Trader and Transporter
	Q4.1 Illiterate	Q4.2 Primary	Q4.3 Secondary	Q4.4 High School	Q4.5 Vocational	Q4.6 University

Q4. Education Level						
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Assessment Questions	Ye s	N o	*Agre e		**Disagre e		General Remarks & Descriptive Answers
			1	2	3	4	
Q5. Knowledge on Zoonotic Diseases (Yes/No Questions)							
Q5.1. Are you aware that animals are capable of transmitting diseases to humans? (Please circle relevant answer)							
Q5.2. Are you aware that living and working close to the bats can increase risk of contracting certain diseases? (Please circle relevant answer)							
Q5.3. Do you know how the diseases are transferred from the bats to humans?							

having direct contact with guano, urines and carcasses increases the risk of getting bat related zoonotic disease?							
Q6.3. Do you agree or not working in the cave does not put you at risk of contracting bat related zoonotic disease?							
Q6.4. Do you agree or not bat droppings/manure does not contain any infectious disease agent?							
Q7. Current Risks Management Practices (Yes/No Questions)							
Q7.1. Are you usually not eating snacks and drinking during bat-guano collection?							
Q7.2. Do you wash your hands before eating and drinking when you are inside and outside the caves?							
Q7.3. Do you wash your hands after attending to any of the							

caves/harvesting bat guano?							
Q7.4. Do you think washing hands is important after handling the bat guano?							
Q7.5. Do you always apply soap when washing hands?							
Q7.6. Do you use any protective clothing before attending to the caves?							
Q7.7. Do you usually change clothes after leaving the caves?							
Q7.8. Do you use a face mask when attending any of the caves?							
The end of the initial assessment sheet.							
Note: * . 1 = Strongly agree . 2 = Agree ** . 3 = Disagree . 4 = Strongly Disagree							

ANNEX 5: ENTIRE LIST OF RESULTS FROM PROPORTIONAL PILING FOR SEASONAL CALENDAR OF HEALTH PROBLEMS

Table 20. Complete list of results for seasonal calendar of health problems

Group	Health Concern	Peak Season	Possible Causes
FBGKPT	Flu	Nov - Feb	Respiratory viruses, colder months
FBGKPT	Persistent cough	Dry season (Dec, April)	Dust, airborne irritants
FBGKPT	Breath difficulty	Nov - Jan	Seasonal changes, work-related exposures
FBGKPT	Eye soreness	Rainy season (May, Sept)	Irritants, seasonal allergens
FBGKPT	Headaches	Rainy season	Environmental factors, stress
MBGKPT	Flu	Jan, Aug	Respiratory viruses
MBGKPT	Eye soreness	Dry season (Dec - Feb)	Dust, cave irritants
MBGKPT	Nose soreness	Dry season	Dust, allergens
MBGKPT	Skin rash	Rainy season	Moisture, irritants, allergens
MBGKPT	Malaria	Rainy season	Mosquito breeding
TTBGKPT	Chronic cough	Dry season (Dec, Jan)	Dust, respiratory irritants
TTBGKPT	Breath difficulty	Dry season	Dust, colder temperatures
TTBGKPT	Flu	Rainy season (Oct)	Typical flu seasonality

Group	Health Concern	Peak Season	Possible Causes
TTBGKPT	COVID-19	Sept (needs confirmation)	Further investigation needed
TTBGKPT	Zoonotic diseases	Dry season (Feb)	Needs investigation into specific diseases and causes
FBGDBG	Flu	Rainy season (Nov, Dec)	Typical flu seasonality
FBGDBG	Persistent cough	May, June	Needs investigation into causes
FBGDBG	Sore throat	Nov, Dec	Shared viral/environmental triggers with flu
FBGDBG	Skin rash	Rainy season (Sept, Oct)	Humidity, fungal growth, irritants
FBGDBG	Eye soreness	Nov, Dec	Shared viral/environmental triggers with respiratory issues
MBGDBG	Skin rash	Rainy season (Sept, Oct)	Moisture, irritants, allergens
MBGDBG	Eye soreness	Dry season	Dust, cave irritants
MBGDBG	Breath difficulty	Year-round	Challenging cave environment, not seasonal
MBGDBG	Flu	Rainy season (Oct)	Typical flu seasonality
MBGDBG	Fever	Less clear seasonality	Needs investigation into causes

ANNEX 6: DETAIL PERCENTAGES OF COMMITMENT TO EACH GOOD PRACTICES OF THE TWO INTERVENTIONS BY GROUPS

Table 21. Detail percentages of commitment to each good practices of the two interventions by group

Group Name	Mask (%)	Gloves (%)	Boot (%)	Hats (%)	Goggles (%)	Raincoat (%)	Hand Wash (%)	Have Hand Wash Station (%)	Daily Wash cloth (%)	Avg. Own Resource to use (%)
FBGKPT	0	71	0	43	0	0	50	0	100	11
MBGKPT	0	36	0	86	0	0	71	0	71	28
TTBGKPT	100	100	0	100	0	0	100	100	100	100
FBGBBG	62	77	0	100	0	0	31	0	100	44
MBGBBG	50	58	0	100	0	0	58	0	100	46

ANNEX 7: A BROCHURE FOR DEMONSTRATION-BASED EDUCATION ON ZOOZOSES

- Animals may carry disease organisms that can cause illness in humans. **Zoonotic diseases or zoonoses**, are diseases of animals that can be transmitted – or transferred- to humans.
- Awareness of these diseases, and their means for spread is important so strategies can be developed to minimize the risk of exposure for responders.
- The spread of disease can occur by direct and indirect transmission methods. Direct spread of a disease may occur through contact with an infected animal, ingestion of the pathogen, or through inhalation (or aerosol) exposure. Indirect methods involve fomites – or inanimate objects that can transfer pathogens – and vectors – living organisms able to transmit pathogens – most commonly insects. Let's look at these routes a bit closer.
- Direct transmission of pathogens can occur from exposure to infected animals, its body fluids – such as urine, feces, saliva, blood or possibly milk – as well as its tissues – either through lesions, carcasses, or during parturition. Entry of the organism occurs following contact with the mucous membranes, such as the eyes, nose, or mouth but can also enter through open wounds or breaks in the skin.

2

- Aerosol transmission involves the transfer of infectious diseases in droplets spread through the air, which are then inhaled. Most microorganisms are not able to survive for extended periods of time within aerosol droplets, and as a result, close proximity to the infected animal is generally required for disease transmission.
- Aerosol transmission can also occur when infected droplets from urine, feces, or birthing material or when these fluids get stirred up from contaminated soil or dust and inhaled.
- Another route of transmission occurs through ingestion of the organism, either through food or water which has been contaminated by infected fecal material or by eating undercooked contaminated meat.
- Some zoonotic diseases can be transmitted indirectly. Fomite transmission involves inanimate objects that become contaminated from an infected animal, which can then serve as a means of transfer for the microorganism. Contacting these items, followed by exposure to your body (eyes, nose, mouth), can increase the risk for disease.
- Mosquitoes, ticks, mites and flies are common disease carrying vectors. Lastly, many disease agents can survive for extended periods of time in soil or other organic material like bedding or manure, animals or humans can then acquire the disease agent from the environment through inhalation or aerosol, oral consumption, direct contact, or via fomites as discussed in previous slides.
- Therefore, environmental contamination should not be ignored but recognized as a potential means of infection that needs to be controlled.

3

- It is important to remember that disease transmission can occur without animals exhibiting obvious clinical signs of disease. These animals may be referred to as a reservoir and may harbor pathogenic organisms, without injury to itself, but serve as a source of infection to others, including humans. Equally important is knowing that not all pathogens are spread by all routes of transmission. Understanding which disease causing organism you are up against, will help in determining which routes of transmission will be of concern during your activities.
- This list shows a few zoonotic disease examples, some of which you may be familiar with including:

- SAR-Cov2
- Rabies
- Ringworm
- Salmonellosis
- Tuberculosis
- Covid-19
- Avian influenza
- NiV
- Cryptosporidiosis
- E. coli wv

4

- While response activities will involve interacting with animals – generally infected animals – avoiding exposure to zoonotic disease may not be feasible. It is important to protect yourself against these zoonotic diseases while working with animals, or in their environment to decrease the risk of becoming ill.
- One of the best protections against any disease is washing your hands. This simple task can greatly reduce the chance of transferring a pathogen from animals to yourself.
- Minimizing contact with infected animals can reduce the risk of disease transmission. Since some pathogens can be transmitted from animals to humans through ingestion, do not eat or drink in animal areas.
- Gloves should be worn when working with sick animals or those that you are unaware of their health status (remember that infected animals do not always appear sick).
- Gloves should be worn when working with sick animals or those that you are unaware of their health status (remember that infected animals do not always appear sick).
- Wearing gloves does not replace good hand washing habits- wash hands in warm water and soap after removing gloves.

5

- Aerosol transmission occurs when infected droplets are passed through the air. Prevention steps against aerosol transmission includes ensuring adequate ventilation, especially if entering enclosed production facilities. Additionally, control the amount of dust generated in animal housing areas. This can damage the protective cells in the respiratory tract and contribute to exposure of contaminated particles in that can cause disease. Wearing masks, such as an N-95 respirator – can help to prevent inhaling contaminated particles in certain situations such as when handling infectious animals or their tissues, assisting with calving, or using a power washer to clean animal areas.

• Biosecurity for Zoonotic Diseases

Route of Transmission	Possible Biosecurity Measures
Direct Contact	Limit contact with infected animals Hand washing Personal protective equipment
Fomites	Cleaning and disinfection procedures Hand washing Personal protective equipment
Aerosol	Personal protective equipment
Ingestion	Cleaning and disinfection procedures
Vectors (e.g. insects)	Pest management procedures

6

ANNEX 8: THE COMMUNITY'S MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

8a. Phnom Romsay Sak Forestry Protected Community's Organization Structure

8b. Phnom Kuhear Loung Forestry Protected Community's Organization Structure

